

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th December 2021

Accepted: 25th December 2021

Online: 30th December 2021

KEY WORDS

*younger generation,
remain unnoticed*

VIDEO GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5830533>

ABSTRACT

In the age of digital technology there are a variety of ways to learn the language and apply it in practice. Undoubtedly, to develop speech, it is useful to read books in the original and watch films without translation. However, in addition to them, we can add some video games that can combine the features of this certain type of art. In this article it has been talked about the role of video games as an additional material during the study of a foreign language and their impact on speech. This article introduces the video games as additional material in practicing and improving English entirely as well as develop listening and reading skills.

Introduction

Currently, one of the exercises that can attract the attention of a person for a long time is game. Since games are a fun activity by their own nature, they are better accepted than other types of exercises such as doing lessons, reading books etc. But the article is accented to unusual games. According to statistics, a large part of the younger generation is spending their free time in front of computers and other gadgets, of course, also manifests itself as the education of students. In this situation, it will be desirable to take it in the right direction without hindering the interest of children. Many video games are created for a purpose that is something beyond human attention. As an example, the game series "Assassins creed" take place on a particular period of history, briefly touching on the

lifestyle of the people of that time, their attitude to each other and politics. Alas, such aspects remain unnoticed and do not go beyond the basic essence of the game. That's why video games take 2nd and 3rd places in learning something. Let's talk about whether it is possible or not to learn foreign language through video games. At first we need to divide the games into the main 3 groups, which can help improve speech:

- Games created for language learning
- Games in a foreign language, not specifically designed for language learning
- Online games

Computer games programmed to learn foreign language

There are a lot of computer games programmed to learn foreign language in the internet and you can easily find dozens of games for learning English. Basically, such games are suitable for those who are beginning to learn the language. Because they are aimed at learning the initial knowledge and the formation of simple skills: various word games, such as learning the alphabet, remembering words, creating simple phrases, guessing words, remembering them. As an example, I'll come up with a few of them.

Busuu[1] for iOS or Android platforms. The studying of language is carried out on the principle of "10 minutes per day". The schedule of training is determined by itself, and the level of complexity is defined by the initial test. Busuu supports 12 languages. One of the main aspects of the application is the network in which the user communicates with native speakers and may be able to communicate with other users. As a drawback Busuu's free options are limited. For a personal training program, you need to pay an additional fee for entering the dictionary and grammar lessons. It is recommended to download because of its advantages such as:

- Google editorial selection
- EdTech Global Awards 2019 finalist in the Nomination " Best language application " dtgv 2018 award winner
- More than 100 million users
- 5th places in the rating of the most popular language applications on Google Play

Simpler[2] for iOS or Android platforms. For the ability to present exercises in the form of a game, the program is perfectly adapted for learning language by the whole

family. The program does not offer testing for English language detection. User can easily choose the complexity of game "for beginners" or "advanced". At your disposal there is a summary with a language simulator, theoretical material and a dictionary. Most interesting exercises will be available only after payment of the account. It is recommended to download because of its advantages such as:

- More than 1 million downloads on Google play
- Ranked 4th in the rating of free apps on Google Play

LingoDeer[3] for iOS or Android platforms. The app is popular among those who are learning Asian languages. LingoDeer classic methods are flash cards, tests, language achievements in the educational process are created based on statistics. After completing the first lesson, the next lesson can be accessed only after switching to a paid account. With a Premium subscription, users also get the opportunity to download mini-recordings with grammar rules for offline reading. It is recommended to download because of its advantages such as:

- Synchronization of the 2019 learning process on Google Play (the results will be saved regardless of the change of the device)
- Possibility to work offline for children under 3 years of age
- Including a reminder system adapted for the whole family, so as not to miss another lesson

The contribution of such games in the study of a foreign language, in the creation of a basis and in the strengthening of speech is

unequivocally great. Unfortunately, there is a drawback to this type of Game:

- Make you bored
- It is often possible to meet the same assignments
- Some programs are conditionally free to learn the language

Popular video games and their impact on language learning

It is no secret that in the study of a foreign language, reading books in its original form, watching movies and serials without translation will help to improve speech development. Among these useful tools can undoubtedly include some of the computer games. The games, which will be useful in strengthening speech, it should be composed of interesting stories and heroes, in addition to the fact that there must be a lot of texts and conversations. Because these criteria can quickly attract and captivate gamers' attention. As advantages of role play games it can be:

- Professional dubbing with subtitles.
- Different instructions, letters, lore and many other texts.
- Involvement of the player in the process. Gamer wants to know how the events will happen, how the story will end.
- The destiny of the heroes and the end of the story directly depend on the player.

The games basically have simple texts, but the speech of the heroes can cause difficulties in understanding. Like movies, it can be recommended as material for listening to games, if the level of language knowledge is good, at least it allows you to read simple texts. If there are problems with

understanding speech, the subtitles will help, fortunately, they are available in all games. In addition to films and books, they can be used regularly: if the story is interesting, then it is easier to comprehend and try to go to the end of it. A few examples of successful video games with rich interesting stories and heroes are presented:

Life is Strange[4] is an adventure game that begins as a simple story about the friendship of two teenager girls and changes into a detective quest full of fantastic elements. The peculiarity of the game is that the protagonist constantly participates in conversations, where it is necessary to make a difficult choice: to try not to lose friends, while helping others. Choosing between two people and so on. Your decisions depend on how the story develops and ends – there are two possible endings in the game. As positive sides it can be shown that:

- There are the abundance of dialogues
- There is the opportunity to listen again and pause
- The presence of a subtitle and the writing of the protagonist's own thoughts in the diary.

Sherlock Holmes: Crimes And Penalties[5] This is the detective story where it must be determined the murder during the certain period of times. Investigation is often published in conversations and texts, the basis of excerpts from books amalgamated, so it is important to comprehend the situation which was written in the texts. In this process, it can be easily enrich vocabulary significantly. The game NPC (Non-Player

Character) pronounced well, the variety of accents are presented, and the characters speak clearly and slowly, which makes listening even more advanced. As good sides it can be shown that:

A large part of the reader will know whether to communicate,

The choice of sentences and the presence of several endings encourage the passing of the game over and over again.

The Last of Us.[6] Very useful for learners of English. In the game you can be faced with excellent voice, interesting communication, in addition, there are very good phrases and collocations during the speech. English is difficult to learn only with games. Examples for good sides: Professional dubbing, relation between parents and children, world rich with written literature.

Bioshock: Infinite.[7] Special detective Booker Dewitt comes to town to find a girl named Elizabeth. The fact that the game has a deep storyline and incredible heroes is one of its main aspects. At the beginning, we know that only Dewitt needs to find a girl. Why detective is looking for her, why the policemen in Colombia persecute Booker as a particularly dangerous criminal – all answers we will find out from conversations, audio recordings, videos during the game. Good sides are:

An abundance of dialogues, the world with rich written literature, the choice of sentences and the presence of several endings

The **Mass effect**[8] series is one of the more popular games in the RPG (role play games) style games. A significant part of the game is rich in such processes as communication, resolution of various disagreements and

discussions, participation in political issues. Professional dubbing and exciting plot are its main aspect which, of course, help to attract the attention. For advantages sides it may be given: Dialogues all define the attitude towards the protagonist, there are several endings, a large part of the game is the passage of communication.

Games like these have the right to stand in the same line as movies and books in speech improvement, so it would be worthwhile to use them wisely during learning language.

An unusual way to develop knowledge in a foreign language: online games

Online games are one of the activities that have the most interest among young people today. As an example, if we take as an example the game WoW (world of Warcraft), millions of players spend 5 and more hours in front of the screen to win the championship. There are also specific benefits of online games. This is also when you complete the game assignments together with foreign players. In order to win in such games, participants need to play in harmony and interact with each other. In such games, the English-speaking audience is large, so that the participants can communicate with each other, learn English during their inclusion in the teams. However, there are several disadvantages of this method, for example, the compatibility of the interlocutor. In most cases, participants of one server can fall into one group, and the fact that they may communicate in their native language. In addition, issues related to the game may be discussed, but nothing else can be talked about. Often, educational programs or games, are considered as a means by which one can learn to speak English. This is not

entirely true. Games and training programs allow you to improve your vocabulary, vocabulary, reading skills, understand speech, but they do not teach language separately. Without any doubt, vocabulary and grammar are necessary for understanding, and there are benefits from these language learning programs, games. But in fact, the ability to speak is a more difficult matter to develop from them. Online games do not fit to this purpose. Yes, there are a lot of players and you need to chat with them or communicate, but in most cases this communication is sharp and does not deviate from the theme of the game.

Conclusion

Summing up, each type of games has its own unique advantages and disadvantages, and for each of them there are its own users. The games that are programmed to engage in speech are appropriate for people who are beginning to learn foreign language. For those who have a high level of language proficiency, however, they can use video games as an experiment and speech reinforcement. Due to the fact that they are just as useful and time-consuming as foreign works, we are confident that using them both during speech reinforcement will make learning a foreign language more interesting and effective.

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